

ADOPTION OF DIGITAL FINANCIAL SERVICES AND ITS IMPACT ON FINANCIAL BEHAVIOR: A REVIEW OF LITERATURE

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ABSTRACT

The main purpose of the study is to identify factors influencing adoption of digital financial services. This paper systematically represents the existing amount of research papers, including the factors affecting adoption of digital financial services. The author identified factors that influence adoption of digital financial services, including compatibility, financial cost, quality of system, unwillingness to change, regulations and laws, and digital infrastructure. The second aim of this study is to discuss the objectives, research methodology, research design, variables tested, and findings of previous studies through a systematic literature review methodology. This paper highlights the adoption of digital financial services, including adoption of mobile banking, internet banking, digital payments, and payment cards, and also highlights the impact of adoption of digital financial services on financial behaviour through a systematic review methodology; therefore, it is found that money usage significantly affects consumer spending and finds a positive correlation between overspending behaviour and mobile payment use. In addition, the study finding implies that an increase in mobile banking services leads to an increase in savings management. At the end of the study paper, author identified the research gaps in this field.

Keywords: Digital Financial Services, Adoption Factors, Mobile Banking, Financial Behavior, Systematic Literature Review

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1. INTRODUCTION

In the past few years, the rapid digital transformation in the financial industry has led banking and financial institutions to adopt digital technology for providing financial services. Financial products and services delivered through digital channels are more convenient and easily accessible, that is why individuals prefer digital transactions over cash transactions. Digital finance has the potential to provide innovative ways for bank, financial institutions, and fintech companies to reach new customers hence, many bank, fintech companies and financial institutions, have also begun to offer basic banking and financial services through digital technology that include mobile banking, internet banking, payment cards, and digital payments, to reach those customers. Digital finance enables millions of individuals to access and use financial services through digital infrastructure without going to bank and financial institutions.

1.1. Digital Finance: Digital finance refers to access and use of all basic banking and financial services, such as saving, investment, loans, credit and debit cards, and insurance, through digital channels like mobile banking, internet banking, and payment cards.

According to a **Mc Kinsey** report digital finance is a financial service delivered via mobile payments, internet, or cards.

Digital financial services expand the delivery of traditional banking services to customers through innovative technologies like internet banking, mobile phone-enabled solutions, electronic money models, and digital payment platforms. **Abbasi et al, (2017).**

Digital finance has several benefits to financial services users, digital finance providers, governments and the economy such as increasing access to finance among poor individuals, reducing the cost of financial intermediation for banks and Fintech providers, and increasing aggregate expenditure for government. **K.Ozili et al,(2018)**

1.2. Digital Financial Services in India

In the year 2012, the payment system experienced rapid growth driven by technological advancements, government regulations, increased mobile penetration, and the availability of low-cost internet services, resulting in significant improvements in the digital payment system. On August 28, 2014, the Pradhan Mantri Jan Dhan Yojana was launched to provide banking services to beneficiaries. This initiative was later linked with the Aadhaar card. The Jan Dhan account, Aadhaar card, and mobile application were integrated to form the JAM Trinity, aimed at enhancing digital banking. The JAM strategy aims to transfer financial benefits directly into beneficiaries' accounts to facilitate Direct Benefit Transfer (DBT). The total number of DBT beneficiaries increased from 108 crore in the year 2013-2014 to 104.8 crore beneficiaries in the year 2023-2024, **according to the Ministry of Finance.** Government policies such as demonetization and Digital India have significantly contributed to the growth of digital financial services. On April 11, 2016, the Unified Payments Interface (UPI) was launched by the National Payments Corporation of India to facilitate the payment system in India. According to NPCI, the total transaction value of UPI in India was 117.6 billion in the year 2023. The BHIM app was also launched in the same year on December 30, 2016. **According to the Ministry of Finance,** the total volume of digital payment transactions grew from 2.071 crore in 2017-2018 to 13,462 crore in 2022-2023.

1.3. Mobile Banking: - The use of a mobile device to conduct financial and banking transactions is referred to as mobile banking. The volume of mobile transactions from July to December 2023 was 62.95 billion, compared to 45.58 billion during the same months in 2022, according to the **Worldline India report 2023.**

1.4. Internet Banking: - Internet banking, also known as e-banking or online banking, is an online service provided by financial institutions and banks that allows individuals to conduct financial transactions through the internet.

1.5. Payments cards: - These are issued by banks and financial institutions to their customers to perform financial transactions

1.6. Debit Cards: These cards are issued by banks to their account holders. Account holders can withdraw amount up to the balance present in their bank account. These cards are also called ATM cards. The volume of debit card transactions in the financial year 2021-2022 was 3.9 billion, and in the financial year 2022-2023, it was 3.4 billion, **according to the Global Fintech Fest 2023 report.**

1.7. Credit Cards: Credit cards are issued by financial institutions and banks to users. These cards are used for borrowing purposes. Users can withdraw or spend amount beyond the balance present in their account, but they have to repay the borrowed amount later. The volume of credit card transactions in the financial year 2021-2022 was 2.2 billion, and in the financial year 2022-2023, it was 2.9 billion, according to the **Global Fintech Fest 2023 report.**

1.8. Digital Payment: Digital payment is an online payment system through which individuals can make payments electronically. **According to the Ministry of Finance**, the total volume of digital payment transactions grew from 2.071 crore in 2017-2018 to 13,462 crore in 2022-2023.

1.9. Financial Behaviour According to Perry and Morris, financial behaviour is defined as the management of a person's savings, expenditures, and budget.

Whereas Xiao 2008 asserts that human activities related to money management, such as cash, savings, and credit, are regarded as financial behaviour.

2. REVIEW METHODOLOGY

2.1. The Present Paper Objectives are: (i) To identify factors influencing the adoption of digital financial services through a review of literature (ii) To discuss objectives, research methodology, research design, variables tested, and findings of previous studies through a review of literature (iii) To identify research gaps in this field for future studies

2.2. Data Sources

The data was collected from secondary sources. A search for journal articles related to the adoption of digital financial services and their impact on financial behaviour was reviewed using keywords such as factors affecting m-banking adoption, internet banking adoption, digital banking adoption, digital payment adoption and impact of mobile banking, internet banking, digital payment on financial behaviour through search engines like Research Gate and Google Scholar. The collected articles were sourced from Research Gate, Emerald, Science Direct, Sage, and Springer.

2.3. Review Process

The Present paper conduct a review of literature on the topic adoption of digital financial services and its impact on financial behaviour in three stages as suggested by **Armstrong et al. (2012) and Turner et al. (2013)**: (i) identifying the literature, (ii) analysis of literature and (iii) categorizing articles.

Stage I: Identifying the Literature: This study, done during the time period between July and August in the year 2024, and open access, full text-reviewed papers, was taken from the year 2013 to 2024. Studies that were done in the context of digital financial services are given preferences, including 20 studies in the paper on the topic of factors influencing adoption of digital financial services and included 8 studies in the paper on the topic of adoption of mobile banking, internet banking, digital banking, and digital payments; 20 research papers included on the topic of adoption of mobile banking, internet banking, digital payment, credit cards, and their impact on financial behaviour, which are considered to be saving behaviour, spending behaviour, and expenditure behaviour.

Stage II: Analysis of Literature: All 48 research papers were identified and analysed according to the number of papers published and distributed in the year and the continent-wise distribution of papers, which are represented in Table No. 1 and Figure No. 1.

Stage III: Arranging Articles: All 20 research articles are classified according to the factors influencing adoption of digital financial services, and other 28 research papers are chronologically arranged based on the objectives in review of literature TableNo. 2 and Table No. 3 in tabular form, including details such as authors, variables influencing adoption of digital financial services, objectives, research methodology, research technique, tests performed, and findings.

2.4. Review Paper Analysis

After analysis of 48 research papers, most of the studies were done in the years 2016, 2017, 2018, 2020, and 2021. 4 research papers were published in the year 2016, 6 research papers were published in the year 2017, 6 research papers were published in the year 2018, respectfully in the years 2020 and 2021, 6 and 12 research papers were published. In the year 2023, 4 research were published. The selected studies are from the Asia continent (India, China, Jordan, Malaysia, Iran, Japan, Thailand, Taiwan, Jakarta, Indonesia), the South Africa continent (Zimbabwe), the West Africa continent (Ghana, Nigeria), the East Africa continent (Kenya, Tanzania), and the North East Africa continent (Sudan), and the Europe continent (Germany).

Table 1. Year wise publication and distribution of reviewed papers in number

S.No.	Year of publication	Author
1.	2013	Joyce mumbi et al (2013).
2.	2014	Karma, N.G., Ibrahim, S.B., & AliA. H. (2014).
3.	2015	Mortimer,G., Neale, L., Hasan, S. F. E.& Benjamin D. (2015).Yadav R et al (2015).
4.	2016	Bhatt, A., & Bhatt, S. (2016)Shankar et al (2016) Boateng, H., Adam, D.R., Okoe, A.F., Anning-Dorson, T., 2016.Wamaitha Kirte P. et al (2016).
5.	2017	Mehrad, D., &Mohammadi, S. (2017), Mani A. Nandhi (2017)Sheikh, B.A. (2017), Munyegera G K et al (2017) Ky Serge et al (2017), Cobla G A M et al (2017)
6.	2018	Chawla, Deepak., & Joshi, Himanshu. (2018)Seethamraju, R., and Diatha, K. S., (2018) Patel, K.J., Patel, H.J., 2018 Gitau, A. N. (2018). Riyadi et al (2018), Meyll T et al (2018).
7.	2019	Das, K. K. and Mahapatra R., (2019) Anouze, A.L.M., Alamro, A.S., 2019, Skogqvist J M et al (2019).
8.	2020	Ariffin, N. H. M., Ahmad, F., and Haneef, U. M., (2020)Oyelami,L.O. & Adebiyi,S.O. (2020). Shruti, J. (2020), Vaishnava, S.R. (2020).Ashik, S.J.S. (2020). Shishany Amar AI et al, (2020),
9.	2021	Chaveesuk, S., Khalid, B. and Chaikasoonthorn, W., (2021)Balakrishnan, V. (2021). Kaur, S.J, &Ali, L., & Hassan, M.K., &Emran, M.E. (2021).Liao, C.F.& Chen, C.D. (2021) Tang, Y. M., Chau, K. Y., Hong, L., Ip, Y. K. and Yan, W., (2021) Jose et al (2021). Loaba et al (2021), Dr. D Padmavati et al (2021)Anene I A et al (2021), Naito H et al (2021) Mensah Michael N.A et al (2021), Biswas s et al, (2021).
10.	2022	Kumari, K., & Singh, R., & Paul, J. (2022). Anane, I., & Nie, F. (2022).
11.	2023	Tater, D. B., & John, D.K. (2023). Nikhitha at al (2023). Akilesh et al (2023), Bakhtiyorovna B Z et al (2023)
12.	2024	Richard et al (2024).

Figure 1: Continent wise distribution of review articles (in percentage)

3. RESULTS AND FINDINGS

Table 2. Represent the factors that affect the adoption of digital financial services of Previous Research Papers.

S.No.	Mobile Banking	Internet Banking	Digital payments	Payments cards	Author	Factors
1.	√				Karma etal (2014)	Perceived Ease of Use, Perceived Risk, Perceived Usefulness, Trust, Behavioural Intention
2.	√				Mortimer etal (2015)	Perceived Credibility, Perceived Ease of Use, Perceived Risk, Perceived Usefulness
3.		√			Yadav Ret al (2015)	Subjective norms and Attitude, Perceived Behavioural control, Perceived usefulness
4.	√				Amola Bhatt and Shahir Bhatt (2016)	Time effectiveness, Safety, Convenience, Ease Navigation, operational Simplicity
5.		√			Boateng, H., Adam, D.R., Okoe, A.F., Anning-	Social feature, effect of websites' trust, Compatibility with lifestyle and online customer services
					Dorson, T (2016)	
6.	√				Shankar etal (2016)	Usefulness, compatibility, social influence; ease of use; security and self-efficacy, privacy risk; and financial cost, Awareness;
7.	√				Mehrad & Moham madi (2017)	Attitude, Perceived Ease of Use, Trust, Intention.
8.	√				Chawla & Joshi (2018)	Attitude, age, gender, occupation, experience, qualification, marital status, and income, perceived usefulness, perceived convenience, perceived lifestyle perceived trust, perceived efficiency

9.			√		Seethamraju & Diatha (2018)	Perceived loss of control, costs of technologies, customer's background, security implications, suppliers influence, tax, poor digital infrastructure, bureaucracy, lack of trust, inadequate access to and poor reliability of digital technologies
10.		√			Patel, K.J., Patel, H.J., (2018)	Perceived security, perceived usefulness and social influence, perceived ease of use
11.			√		Das & Mahapatral (2019)	Security, privacy, and convenience
12.		√			Anouze, A.L.M., Alamro, A.S., (2019)	Reasonable price, perceived ease of use, security and perceived usefulness, stand out
13.			√		Ariffin et al (2020)	Performance and effort expectancy, habit, privacy, social influence, facilitating conditions, intentions, and perceived security
14.				√	Shishany Amar AI et al (2020)	Welfare of the individual, expenditure level, theft and fraud, regulations and laws, and psychological behavior.
15.			√		Tang et al (2021)	Service quality, perceived security, perceived risk, perceived ease of use, compatibility, social influence, and age
16.			√		Chaveesu k et al (2021)	Perceived ease of use, attitude, social distancing, and satisfaction

Adoption of Digital Financial Services and Its Impact on Financial Behavior: A Review of Literature

17.			√		Vimala Balakrishnan (2021)	Compatibility, effort expectancy, perceived usefulness, security, trust, performance expectancy, and facilitating conditions, perceived ease of use, cost of use, complexity, perceived danger, privacy concerns unwillingness to change
18.	√	√	√	√	Isaac Anane Fengying Nie (2022)	Awareness, effort expectancy, facilitating conditions, security and privacy, and transaction cost, self-efficacy
19.	√				Tater et al (2023)	Innovation, responsiveness and communication, security and privacy, accessibility and reliability, and openness and trust
20.	√	√	√	√	Richard et al (2024)	Discomfort, task-technology fit, quality of systems, connectivity, perceived cost, and self-efficacy, perceived usefulness, trust

From the Table 2 it is interpreted that factors such as perceived usefulness, subjective norms, attitude, and perceived behaviour control were found to be significant factors in the intention to adopt internet banking, whereas perceived risk was found to be insignificant variables in the intention to adopt internet banking by consumers (Yadav et al., 2015). Trust, website social features, compatibility with lifestyle, and online customer services have a positive impact on customer's intentions to adopt internet banking, while ease of use has no significant impact on customer's intentions to adopt internet banking by Boateng, H., Adam, D.R., Okoe, A.F., and Anning-Dorson, T (2016). According to Chawla & Joshi (2018). Age, gender, occupation, experience, qualification, marital status, and income have a moderating effect on the attitude to adopt mobile banking, whereas educational background has an insignificant effect on the attitude to adopt mobile banking. It was identified from the study that welfare of individuals, psychological behaviour, theft and fraud, laws and regulations, knowledge of credit cards, and level of expenditure influence adoption of credit cards Shishany Amar AI et al (2020). Perceived risk negatively influences the intention of the consumer to use WeChat payments Tang et al., (2021).

Table 3. Statistical Representation of Objectives, Research Methodology, Research Technique, Statistical Tools, Findings of the Previous Research Papers

S.N O.	Author Year	Adoption of Digital financial services	Adoption of Digital financial services and its impact on financial behaviour	Objectives	Research Methodology	Research Technique	Statistical Tools	Findings
1.	Joyce mumbi et al (2013)		v	To determine the effect of mobile banking on the saving culture among residents of Molo town.	Descriptive	Simple Random Sampling	Multiple regression modelling, Correlation, Regression	Residents of Molo Town use the M-PESA account more than the other mobile banking services and found that the use of mobile banking help them to improve their saving behaviour and hence avoid overspending because it has become easy for them to access mobile banking services by the smart phone.
2.	Wamait ha Kirite P. et al (2016)		v	To study the effects of mobile banking on savings of MSEs in Gikomba Market	Descriptive	Stratified Random Sampling	Correlation	The study found a positive relationship between micro and small enterprises savings and use of mobile banking. MSEs use mobile banking for various purposes, including stock purchases efficiently, sales transactions, receiving payments, money transfers, payment for
								goods and services, and increasingly use mobile banking for savings, all of which influence their business growth.
3.	Sheikh B A et al (2017)	v		The present study is aimed at knowing the adoption of digital banking services in India	Descriptive	Stratified sampling	Chi-Square	In this study, it was found that 41% of banking customers adopt digital banking services, in which MNCs were found to be major adopters of digital banking services and self-employed were the second major adopters of digital banking services.
4.	Ky Serge et al (2017)		v	Investigate whether the use of mobile money can help individuals build savings to face predictable and unpredictable events.	Descriptive		Logit regression model	In the study, evidence shows that the use of mobile money increases the propensity to save money for health emergencies among disadvantaged individuals, such as women, rural people, individuals who have irregular sources of income, and less educated individuals.
5.	Cobla G A M et al (2017)		v	To investigate how the use of the mobile money technology among students affects their spending behaviour.	Descriptive	Simple Random Sampling	Ordinary least squares regression technique	Students who use mobile banking services their spending behaviour is significantly influenced than that of non-users of mobile banking services because mobile money services increase access to finance.
6	Munyegera G K		v	To examine the effect of this	Empirical		Tobit Model,	Findings reveal that the likelihood of borrowing, saving, and

Adoption of Digital Financial Services and Its Impact on Financial Behavior: A Review of Literature

	et al (2017)		financial innovation on their financial behavior			Probit Model, Two Stage least Square Method	receiving remittances is increased by using mobile money services. Additionally, in comparison to households that don't use mobile money services, the corresponding amount of each service is significantly higher among the mobile money household users. In addition, transaction costs, transportation fares, and service charges that are associated with households that proximate to mobile money agents are significantly reduced by this effect of using mobile money services, which increases saving, borrowing, and receiving remittances.
7.	Mani A. Nandhi (2017)	v	To study the effects of EKO mobile banking on the savings behaviour and practices of low-income users in the metropolis of Delhi.			Percentage analysis method	Eko mobile banking has improved the ability of users to save. Saving by using an Eko mobile banking account is trustworthy, safe, and effective, and it has become the best saving instrument among the users. Additionally, Eko mobile banking enabled users to save rather than spend funds on unnecessary expenses; therefore, it has developed better savings habits among the users.
8.	Gitao et al (2018)	v	To investigate the effects of mobile banking on the financial behaviour of university students.	Descriptive	Stratified Random Sampling	Correlation, Regression, Anova	The result of the study show that a significant positive relation was found between mobile banking services and saving behaviour because use of mobile banking services makes easy access to financial services such as saving than going to the bank. Additionally, students are able to have virtual mobile bank accounts that can be accessed and used easily on a smart phone.
9.	Riyadi et al (2018)	v	This study aims to analyze the impact of financial literacy, consumptive behavior, and m-banking services on savings management.	Descriptive	Simple Random Sampling	Multiple Linear Regression Test, T-test, Regression	The linear regression test applied in the study found that an increase in M-banking services leads to an increase in savings management.
10.	Meyll T et al (2018)	v	To investigate the relationship between mobile payments and credit card behavior.	Empirical		Linear Probability model Regression	Costly credit card behaviour is influenced by mobile payment use and includes three behaviours of credit cards, such as paying late fees, minimum payment, and charging over the limit fee; therefore, findings suggest that mobile payment methods also increase individuals spending.

11.	Skogqvist JM et al (2019)	v		To investigate the effect of using mobile money on the savings patterns of individuals.	Empirical	Simple Random Sampling	Linear probability model, Two stage Least square Regression analysis	Mobile money usage has a strong positive correlation with saving behaviour, and results also show that mobile money users save more likely than non-users. In addition, the propensity of low-income individuals have increased to save for uncertain future events and emergent needs.
12.	Shruti et al (2020)	v		To understand cashless payment system usage among consumers	Explanatory	Purposive and Snowball	SEM, Anova	Debit cards, online payment systems, and mobile banking are most commonly used as cashless payment options, and bank transfers, checks, credit cards, mobile wallets, and prepaid cards are the least commonly used as cashless payment modes.
13.	Ramratan Vaishnav et al (2020)	v		To study the adoption of digital financial services in service sector organization	Extensive study	Simple Random Sampling	Anova	An Anova test was performed to study the adoption of digital financial services in different service sector organizations and found that all operations in the oil and gas industry are done in digital mode.
14.	Syed ashik et al (2020)	v		The current research is aimed to study the acceptance and adoption of the e-banking system in India	Descriptive	Simple Random Sampling	Theoretical Analysis	Occupation status was found to have a significant impact on the adoption of digital banking services. In addition, students and employed people use digital banking services more than traditional banking services because they find that digital banking services are more convenient.
15.	Oyelami LO et al (2020)	v		To investigate the determinants of electronic payment adoption and the role of electronic payment on consumers' purchase decisions as well as its effects on consumers' spending growth in Nigeria	Quantitative Method	Simple Random Sampling	Chi-square Test, Anova, Regression	The result of the study shows that various factors influence the use of e-payment, including educational attainment, availability of internet services, mobile banking services, level of income, point of sale devices, and financial inclusion. In addition, results also show that customers purchase decisions are influenced by e-payment use, which increases customer spending.
16.	Biswas et al (2021)	v		To Examine the relationship between mobile financial services and individual financial behavior in India	Empirical Method		Linear Probability Model, Two – Stage least Square Model	The study results show that the adoption of mobile financial services increases individuals' financial outcomes, including increased likelihood of investing, borrowing money from financial institutions, and purchasing insurance. Furthermore, the use of mobile financial services also reduces the gender gap in financial inclusion.
17.	Jit kaur et al (2021)	v		The aim of this study is to analyse the role of in-branch efforts of banks	Qualitative study	Simple Random Sampling	Interview and observation methods	Branch Digital Transformation, in branch communication, the staff's defined roles and customer-centric efforts all have potential to

Adoption of Digital Financial Services and Its Impact on Financial Behavior: A Review of Literature

			on migrating customers from banking to digital banking in India				migrate customers from branch banking to digital banking.
18.	Feng Liao et al (2021)	v	To investigate the relationship between mobile payment, use and financial behaviors	Empirical study		Logit Regression model	A logit regression model was used to study the relationship between financial behaviour and mobile payment use. A negative relation was found between positive financial behaviour and mobile payment use. The outcomes of positive financial behaviour are spending less than income, not having difficulty covering expenses, and not experiencing an overdraft.
19.	Jose et al (2021)	v	To study the digital payment system affects the money saving of the individual COVID times	Descriptive	Simple Random Sampling	Percentage Method	The respondents agreed that using digital payment apps has improved their money saving strategy by eliminating the need for travel expenses. In addition, respondents agreed that they save money in the form of cash back or discounts by using digital payment apps.
20.	Loaba et al (2021)	v	To analyses the impact of the use of mobile banking services on saving	Empirical Study		Logit Regression model	It is observed that there is a 2.4% and 0.83% increase in the likelihood of formal and informal savings when mobile banking services are used. Women are more likely than men to have
			behavior in west Africa				informal savings, but if they use mobile banking services, they are more likely to have formal savings.
21.	Anene I A et al (2021)	v	To determine the extent to which academic librarians are aware and use mobile banking services in Nigeria	Quantitative	Purposive Sampling	Percentage Analysis Method	According to the study, most academic librarians are aware of and regularly use mobile banking services, which include checking account balance, receiving account statements, buying airtime, requesting transactions, transferring funds, and receiving SMS notifications. In addition, the majority of academic librarians agree that the use of mobile banking services facilitates the transfer of funds, solves account inquiries, saves customer time, provides timely responses, reduces cost, and is more convenient for customers. According to the findings, customers save time by adopting and using mobile banking services, which allow them to complete transactions quickly without waiting in line and using paper documentation.
22.	Mensah Michael N.A et al	v	To examines how e-money usage affects	Quantitative and Qualitative methods	Purposive Sampling, Simple	Ordered Logit Model,	Usage of e-money positively influences the spending behaviour of consumers. The different types

	(2021)			consumer spending behaviour through discrete choice analysis considering demographic characteristics		Random Sampling	Anova, Discrete Choice Analysis	of E-money used and expenditures made with the use of E-money both significantly influence consumer expenditure. Additionally, gender, age, and employment status also affect consumer expenditure.
23.	Naito H et al (2021)		v	To examines the effect of the use of mobile money services on borrowing and saving using data from Tanzania			Two-stage least squares estimation	The chances of borrowing increase when the non-users of mobile money accounts experience negative shocks, but the chances of borrowing do not increase for the users of mobile money accounts when they experience negative shocks. Users who adopt mobile money technology's chances of their saving increase compared to non-users. Additionally, the chances of saving also increase for the groups that adopt mobile money technology than the group that uses less liquid savings methods, such as saving through livestock, churches, and commodities.
24.	Dr. D Padmavati et al (2021)		v	To identify and analyse the influence of cashless payment on spending	Descriptive	Convenience sampling	Anova	Expenditure on clothing and accessories, entertainment and communication, food, travel, and home decor products has been increased by the payment made on a cashless basis; thus, it has

Adoption of Digital Financial Services and Its Impact on Financial Behavior: A Review of Literature

			behaviour for the select category of products				influenced the saving behaviour of the users by making payment through the cashless method.
25.	Young Ahn et al (2022)	v	To investigate whether and how mobile payment use influences financial behaviours, particularly overspending behaviours	Empirical Study		Logit Regression model	Overspending behaviour such as management of money, credit card behaviour, and consumption are significantly influenced by the use of mobile payment; a positive relation was found between financial behaviour and use of mobile payment. Users of mobile payments are at higher risk of overspending than non-users.
26.	Nikhitha et al (2023)	v	To analyse the awareness level of customers on digital payments products 2.To find out the reasons for the adoption of digital payments	Descriptive and analytical	Convenience sampling	Anova and Correlation	The level of awareness about digital payments among customers was observed and it was found that they use digital payments to make transactions, transfer funds, pay restaurant bills and buy tickets online. Furthermore, most of the respondents adopted digital payments due to its 24/7 availability, time saving, secure convenience service availability.
27.	Akilesh et al (2023)	v	To identify and analyze the Impact of Digital Payment on Consumers Spending Behaviour	Descriptive	Convenience sampling	Chi-Square, Simple Percentage Analysis	In the research paper, it was found that demographic characteristics such as gender and monthly income of consumers have no impact on spending behaviour, but age and educational qualification have a positive
							impact on consumer spending behaviour.
28.	Bakhtiyorovna B Z et al (2023)	v	To understand the most commonly used Digital Payment Methods and check the cross-tabulation with the frequency of usage.	Descriptive	Convenience sampling	Simple Percentage Analysis, Anova, Sample T Test	UPI is found to be the most commonly used digital payment method, followed by credit cards and debit cards as payment systems among the customers. AEPS, RTGS, and USSD are not used according to the study findings. In addition, Google Pay is used most often among customers as a mobile payment application. Paytm is also used as a mobile payment application, according to the study findings.

4. LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE RESEARCH SCOPE

The review of literature provides detailed information on factors affecting adoption of digital financial services but gives less details on adoption of digital financial services and its impact on financial behaviour. Based on a review of literature, only 48 research articles are identified and analysed, of which 20 are based on factors influencing adoption of internet banking, mobile banking, credit cards, and digital payments; 8 research papers belong to the adoption of digital banking, e-banking, and cashless payments and mobile banking; and 20 research papers are based on the impact of the adoption of mobile banking, internet banking, and digital payment impact on financial behaviour, which include saving, investing, insurance, and spending behaviour. This research paper only covers open-access review papers that are published and unpublished papers. This study does not include many research papers that are published in reputed journals and does not include the TAM and UTAUT models. Only a few research papers that were easily accessed and published in reputed journals are included in the study. The study included only a few prestigious journals; Therefore, other reputable published research papers that the authors could not reach have not been included in the study.

For future research areas, there are several research topics on which study can be done, and they are adoption of mobile banking and its impact on investment and insurance behaviour, credit card usage and their impact on borrowing behaviour, and digital payments. Adoption of technology and its impact on expenditure and saving behaviour. There are fewer studies that are done on the adoption of digital financial services, which include awareness, acceptance, and usage of digital financial services, which would also be done in future studies.

5. CONCLUSION

In this digital era, digital financial services continue to expand, and they have the potential to provide all financial services to millions of users at the same time without reaching to the bank. From the last ten years ago, financial institutions, banks, and fintech companies heavily invested in providing digital financial services through the development of technological innovation. There are various studies done on this subject; therefore, it can be concluded from the study that most of the studies are on factors influencing adoption of digital financial services, and it is found that perceived ease of use, perceived usefulness, reasonable price, accessibility and reliability, and innovation are factors that positively influence adoption of mobile banking, internet banking, and digital payment, but security, privacy concerns, digital infrastructure, theft, and online fraud are factors that negatively influence adoption of digital payments and adoption of internet banking. Many studies can be conducted on the enablers and inhibitors of the adoption of digital financial services, and research can also be done on the topic of the adoption of mobile banking, internet banking, and digital payments and their impact on financial behaviour, as very few research papers are found on these topics. In this 21st century, adoption of mobile banking, adoption of internet banking, digital payments, and UPI are gaining more popularity, and many researchers are doing their studies on this domain.

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Adoption of Digital Financial Services and Its Impact on Financial Behavior: A Review of Literature

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